

11-16 AUGUST 2019
22nd International Conference
on Composite Materials

On the resizing of recycled fibres

E. Sarlin, V. Matrenichev, S. Palola, P. Laurikainen, K. Lahtonen and M. Valden

Faculty of Engineering and Natural Sciences, Tampere University, Finland

CONFERENCE
HOSTS:

CONFERENCE
DESTINATION
SUPPORTERS:

#ICCM22

FiberEUse project

H2020 Grant agreement nr. 730323

Large scale demonstration of new circular economy value-chains based on the reuse of end-of-life fibre reinforced composites

Special characteristics of thermal recycling

- Thermal recycling is typically an energy-wasting process
 - Economical aspects set requirements for the final fibre quality
- Fibre strength reduction [1]
 - Carbon fibres: strength reduction 4%-85%
 - Glass fibres: strength reduction >50%
- Altered fibre surface properties
 - The original sizing is lost which affects the processibility and sensitivity of the fibre and the achievable fibre/matrix adhesion level
 - For carbon fibres also formation of a char-like surface layer is possible

Sizing and resizing processes

- Sizing of virgin fibres is integrated to the continuous fibre production
 - The form of (thermally) recycled fibres is not continuous
 - Different sizing process needed: batch type process by immersion or spraying
- Optimization of the resizing process needed
 - General resizing procedure
 - Need for pre-treatment
 - Sizing application technology
 - Need for post-treatment
 - Resizing solution composition

Objective:

To understand the effect of resizing variables on adhesion in rCF and rGF composites

Selected resizing process and variables

- Immersion of fibre batch in sizing solution
- Studied variables
 - Need for pre-treatment
 - rCF: washing the recycled fibres or acidic treatment
 - rGF: washing recycled fibres
 - Sizing solution composition
 - rCF: film former w%
 - rGF: coupling agent w% and film former w%, pH of the solution
 - Need for post-treatment
 - Rinsing after resizing

After
thermal
treatment

rCF

rGF

After
resizing

Conclusions: resizing of recycled carbon fibres

- The recycled carbon fibre surface is rougher compared to virgin fibre. The diameter and strength of the fibre are decreased but the modulus is similar to virgin fibres.
- The fibre surface has good compatibility with thermoset resin after thermal recycling. The adhesion is not improved after cleaning the fibre surface with aqueous treatment.
- Acidic pre-treatment purifies the carbon fibre surface but decreases the fibre/matrix adhesion.
- The compatibility of the fibre with thermoplastic resin was not affected by adding a film former which is however needed to improve the processibility of the fibres. In larger scales feeding the fibres during compounding is impossible without any sizing.
- The resizing immersion time does not have an effect on the resulting fibre/matrix adhesion.
- The resizing process does not affect the mechanical properties of the fibre.

Conclusions: resizing of recycled glass fibres

- The recycled glass fibre surface is rougher compared to virgin fibre due to the resin residues. The diameter and strength of the fibre are decreased clearly, but the modulus is more similar to virgin fibres.
- Rinsing the fibre before resizing does not affect the achievable fibre/matrix adhesion.
- Increasing absolute and relative (compared to the film former concentration) concentrations of coupling agent in the sizing solution increase the fibre/matrix adhesion.
- The film former concentration did not have an effect on the adhesion but is still needed to protect and improve the processability of the fibres.
- The resizing immersion time does not have an effect on the resulting fibre/matrix adhesion.
- The resizing process is able to improve the mechanical properties of the recycled glass fibres by ~45%.

Acknowledgements

POLITECNICO
MILANO 1863

AERnova
engineering

AK

designaustria®

Istituto di Tecnologie Industriali e Automazione
Consorzio Nazionale delle Ricerche

GreenCoat

BATZ

EDAG

HEAD

HOLONIX
BRING THINGS TO LIFE

RIVIERASCA^{SPA}
glebanite

Tampere University

MAIER

SIEMENS Gamesa
RENEWABLE ENERGY

ACADEMY
OF FINLAND

INVENT

tecnalia Inspiring
Business

NOVELLINI

Fraunhofer
IWU

ICCM22
MELBOURNE
AUSTRALIA

11-16 AUGUST 2019
22nd International Conference
on Composite Materials

University of
Strathclyde

Saubermacher

#ICCM22